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SHORT NOTES / BREVI NOTE

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USE OF TELEMETRY TO MONITOR THE MOVEMENTS
OF PAPILIO MACHAON (Lepidoptera Papilionidae)
AND CHAMAELEO CHAMAELEON (Squamata Chamaeleonidae)

RATIONALE

Telemetry has revolutionised wildlife research by providing scientists with unprecedented insights into the movements and behaviour of animals in their natural habitats. This technology allows for the remote monitoring of wildlife, offering a window into the secretive lives of species that were previously difficult or even impossible to study.

The required equipment typically comprises transmitters attached to target organisms that send signals to receivers, allowing researchers to track the individual animal's movements over considerable distances and time scales (KENWARD, 2001). The employment of equipment with the capacity for long-distance tracking can prove crucial for better understanding migratory movement and associated patterns, habitat preferences and resource use, social behaviour and structures within populations, as well as survival strategies, all critically essential for conservation efforts.

The ability to track wildlife using telemetry provides important information for conservation strategies, helping in the management of species, whether endangered or in need of control such as aliens. Information gathered through telemetry also contributes to more knowledge of ecological dynamics involving target species (CAGNACCI *et al.*, 2010).

Depending on the form of data required, various types of telemetry devices can be utilised, including VHF, GPS, and satellite systems. Each system can offer a suite of advantages in terms of range, accuracy, sampling duration, and data collection capabilities. Choice of device largely depends on research goals, the actual size of the species being studied (this consideration equates with payload capability), and the specific environmental conditions of the study area.

Initially, the technology was developed for tracking movement of macro-vertebrates (CAGNACCI *et al.*, 2010). However, advancements in the field in recent decades have led to a host of other possibilities that allowed the tracking of small insect target species.

In more recent years, insect telemetry has expanded its foci from resource use, movement across the home range, habitat selection preferences and physical distances, to behavioural aspects associated with foraging and strategies allied to multi-generational passage (KISSLING *et al.*, 2014).

AIMS

The present study focused on telemetric monitoring of two unrelated taxa, namely *Papilio machaon* Linnaeus, 1758 and *Chamaeleo chamaeleon* (Linnaeus, 1758). Telemetric work on the Swallowtail butterfly was aimed at establishing an understanding of its ability to move from one island to another of the Maltese archipelago, while monitoring of chameleons was carried out to determine the rate of movement by individuals across a woodland habitat (see more details on its preferred habitat in the Background section below).

BACKGROUND

One of the most studied members of the family Papilionidae is the iconic *Papilio machaon*, a species which occurs within two Zoogeographical Regions, the Palearctic and Nearctic, comprising at least three continents – Europe, Asia, and North America (the species' presence in Africa, west of the Sinai, is currently being investigated). The species, *sensu lato*, has shown a high versatility where habitats are concerned, tending to occupy ecological niches within suitable biotopes from sea-level to approximately 5000 m amsl. Accordingly, considerable research has been published on the species, including studies relating to DNA analysis (OBERTHÜR, 1879; ELLER, 1936; SEYER, 1974, 1976; HIGGINS & RILEY, 1978; CLARKE & LARSEN, 1986; SPERLING, 1990, 1993; SPERLING & HARRISON, 1994; PELLECCIA *et al.*, 2002; VOD *et al.*, 2016; DUPUIS & SPERLING, 2020; DOMAGALA & LIS, 2022). Moreover, since the species is not known to undertake intergenerational passage across vast expanses of sea and inhospitable terrain, as do other species typically known to 'migrate' (such as *Vanessa cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *D. plexippus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Colias croceus* (Geoffroy, 1785) and *Pieris rapae* (Linnaeus, 1758), to name a few notable species), numerous distinct *machaon* subspecies have been described over time (LINNAEUS, 1758; HÜBNER, [1823]; EIMER & FICKERT, 1895; SEITZ, 1906; VERITY, 1911; OBERTHÜR, 1915; TENNENT, 1996; TOLMAN & LEWINGTON, 1998; TARRIER & DELACRE, 2008; TSHIKOLOVETS, 2011). The list of *machaon* subspecies tends to fluctuate in view of endless revisions, with some authors tending to synonymise taxa and others inclined to split the classification further. In a recent publication on the Papilionidae (genus *Papilio*) of the Palearctic region, NAZARI *et al.* (2023) proposed the synonymy of numerous taxa, including *Papilio machaon hispanicus* Eller, 1936, *P. m. emispbyrus* Verity, 1919, and *P. m. syriacus* Eller, 1936 into *P. m. aestivus* Eimer & Fickert, 1895; and *P. m. melitensis* Eller, 1936 into *P. m. sphyrus* Hübner, [1823], among others.

Prolonged isolation is one of the key mechanisms for divergence and the subsequent development of new life forms, although clearly not the only vehicle for this fundamental evolutionary process leading to speciation (DARWIN, 1859; MAYR, 1942; MANI *et al.*, 1990; COYNE & ORR, 2004; BUTLIN *et al.*, 2008; SOBEL *et al.*, 2010; SAFRAN & NOSIL, 2012). Islands provide the ideal field or living laboratory for studying biogeography and evolution (FILSON, 2000). They are especially interesting because they are often incomparably diverse. The setting afforded by islands is often quite unique in terms of habitat and biotic make-up. The likelihood of successful colonization increases with proximity to continental landmasses or older, larger islands, albeit with varying degrees of establishment. Conversely, spatial isolation diminishes gene flow between sub- units of the metapopulation, leading to genetic divergence from populations at the center of origin (MAC ARTHUR & WILSON, 1967; THORPE *et al.*, 1994). Fluctuations in eustatic levels of the oceans, as global climates oscillated between glacial and interglacial periods in geological time, also led to intermittent connectivity between islands and surrounding landmasses. This would have set in motion a dynamic process of immigration and species turnover resulting in competition for niche space, a driving force largely enabled by extinctions (JACKSON & SAX, 2010). Allopatry, which is characteristic of island biogeographic and evolutionary development, arises in a variety of ways, often due to processes asso-

ciated with major geological and climatological events. The process of divergence, as descendant taxa develop unique characteristics and branch out genetically from their ancestral lineage due to vicariance and dispersal, among other mechanisms, is complex. This is particularly so when isolation is intermittent over geological time, allowing introgression to occur (as influxes of immigrant individuals from the parent taxon or the species' 'center of origin' recolonize islands), while speciation has not completed its course. Such are the complexities that will have a profound influence on the evolutionary development of taxa at the various stages of divergence, especially on islands.

Chamaeleo chamaeleon is a fairly versatile predatory lizard species, mostly but not exclusively insectivorous, with a circum-Mediterranean distribution extending across North Africa, parts of southern Europe and the Middle East, and numerous islands. The species' presence outside its natural range is attributed to anthropogenic translocation; as a result, this has led to the establishment of new populations wherever environmental conditions were found to be favourable (CUADRADO, 2014; ANDREONE *et al.*, 2016). This has occurred in a number of countries, including Spain, Portugal, Italy, and Malta (SAVONA-VENTURA, 1985; ANDREONE *et al.*, 2016; BASSO *et al.*, 2019).

It is thought to have been introduced into Malta from the Maghreb in the 1850s by missionaries and released in private gardens in the St. Julian's area (SAVONA-VENTURA, 1985; SCHEMBRI & SULTANA, 1989; SCHEMBRI & LANFRANCO, 1996; SCIBERRAS, 2007). Its dispersal across the main island is thought to have occurred through both natural (escapees) and passive (aided by human agency) means, while the species was clearly transported to the island of Gozo by people.

C. chamaeleon is well adapted to the Mediterranean rocky, dry and sparsely vegetated environment, where it tends to spend considerable time foraging on the ground on karstic terrain where vegetation is sparse, or on low shrubbery. It is also known to occur within synanthropic landscapes, including rural and degraded areas, as well as in proximity to road verges (CUADRADO, 2014; HODAR *et al.*, 2000; pers. field observations – L.F.C./N.G.). This diurnal species tends to climb onto the upper reaches of large shrubs and small trees at dusk where it then spends the night, presumably, to seek safe refuge from potential nocturnal predators such as weasels, snakes, rats, and feral cats (pers. field observations – L.F.C./N.G.). Females of *C. chamaeleon* are known to lay their eggs in areas where the soil cover is loose but not necessarily too deep. The reasons leading to its current policy status remain enigmatic, since there is no sound scientific basis for affording the species protection; given its predatory nature where it is known to consume all manner of invertebrates and also young lizards, including chameleons, it may only be a matter of time before the species requires a monitoring programme for its control.

METHODS

Two species, taxonomically unrelated, were selected for tagging and subsequent tracking via telemetry. The Old-World Swallowtail butterfly, *Papilio machaon*, was selected with a view to investigate (i) its ability to undertake a sea-crossing between two visible islands' coastlines, that is, across the Comino - Gozo channel, a strait of 0.84 km at its shortest distance, and (ii) how long it might take for the tagged individuals on the island of Comino (3.5 km²) before they undertook the crossing to the island of Gozo (67 km²), if at all. The Mediterranean Chameleon, *Chamaeleo chamaeleon*, is essentially a protected alien species of relatively recent colonisation, which has become naturalised. The chosen area of study for the chameleon was Buskett woodland, located on the Rabat-Dingli uplands, on the south-west segment of the mainland (Fig. 1). Both Comino and Buskett form part of the Natura 2000 network of protected areas.

Both taxa were tracked through the use of a VHF radio setup, which included an omnidirectional Yagi antenna, a Biotrack Sika radio-tracking receiver, and VHF radio tags. Equipment was chosen on the basis of cost-efficiency, ease of use, and its capability to track individuals in open spaces as well as in densely vegetated terrain regions.

Fig. 1 — Field research locations of the present study (Base map source: Esri, HERE, Garmin).

In the case of *P. machaon*, butterfly specimens were transported to the island of Comino for release. Once on site, the butterflies, which were transported in small individual cooler boxes, were released into a larger specialized holding net cage prior to tagging and subsequent release. The but-

terflies were chosen based on gender and dimensions, including overall wingspan size, since the larger the individual, the less likely it may be impeded by the weight of the radio tag; ultra-lightweight tags were, in any case, employed so as not to hinder the butterflies' mobility. After the tags were activated, each tag was carefully attached to the underside of the abdomen with a fast-drying superglue, while the aerial was aligned lengthwise, extending beyond the abdomen (Fig. 2), at an angle that would not interfere with the butterfly's flight nor obstruct or alter its natural behavior. For *C. chamaeleon*, tagging took place after nightfall in order to facilitate spotting specimens on tree branches via torch beam lights. Upon tagging (Fig. 3), using slightly heavier tags, 5 to 15 minutes were spent observing each individual chameleon following release to ensure that the tag was properly affixed, and that the animal's mobility was not impaired.

The tagged butterflies were then released one at a time, observing each individual for as long as it remained visible to ensure it was still motile and unhindered by the tag before, then, tracking with the radio-receiver (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2 — (L to R). Process involving the gluing of the tag to the underside of the butterfly's abdomen, through to the moment of release.

Fig. 3 — Adjusting the collar onto which the tag is fixed (left); a tagged specimen immediately after release (right).

Fig. 4 — Tracking the butterfly specimens on foot on the island of Comino, and by motorboat between the islands.

The present research was duly covered by an Environmental Permit (EP 1206/21), issued by the Environment & Resources Authority (ERA). Researchers also had the support of Heritage Malta, the agency responsible for managing parts of the island of Comino and Buskett, both designated Natura 2000 sites.

Limitations — Key among the inadequacies was the fact that only one radio-tracking receiver was employed for the present study; it is acknowledged that an additional one or two units would have provided more precise data collection. It is further acknowledged that radio transmitters may well present a degree of constraint in terms of resulting behaviour to cope with the ‘imposed’ tag (KISSLING *et al.*, 2014; KIM *et al.*, 2016). In the case of the butterflies, it was expected to incur a fair amount of energetic cost in view of the additional weight and bulk, while in the case of the chameleons, an element of discomfort (albeit seemingly minor) as a consequence of the collar was perceived to occur.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The radio signal from the tagged butterflies (two males and one female) that were released on the island of Comino on 28th June was followed over the course of nine field monitoring sessions, between the day of release and 14th July 2021. The tags affixed to these butterflies lasted for much of their lifespan, thus providing meaningful insights into their movement. Telemetry readings indicated that the tagged butterflies crossed the Comino - Gozo channel (Fig. 5), respectively, on 30th June 2021 (SPEC code: P.m.1 ♂ [blue] - freq. 150.010 MHz), 30th June 2021 (SPEC code: P.m.2 ♂ [red] - freq. 150.030 MHz) and 1st July 2021 (SPEC code: P.m.3 ♀ [green] - freq. 151.368 MHz). It should be noted that, at the time of release, *P. machaon's* known larval food-plants, *Foeniculum vulgare* Miller, and *Ruta chalepensis* L., did not appear to be present on the island of Comino. Moreover, nectaring opportunities were also scarce since few plant species were in bloom on the smaller island; these included *Jacobea maritima* ssp. *sicula* N.G. Passal., Peruzzi & Pellegrino (Sicilian silvery ragwort) and *Thymbra capitata* (L.) Cav. (Mediterranean Thyme), together with cultivated *Nerium oleander* L., (Oleander) and *Lantana montevidensis* (Spreng.) Briq. (Trailing Lantana) within or near to hotel grounds. In contrast, the much larger and hillier island of Gozo follows a characteristic of island biogeography in that, among other factors, larger islands (i) support a broader habitat heterogeneity as a consequence to a greater climatic gradient, and (ii) provide a bigger target for immigrant species or individual specimens. The topography of Gozo is also appreciably different and substantially hillier than that of Comino, as a result of which, Blue Clay taluses, completely absent on the latter, are a dominant feature of Gozo’s landscape. Effectively a marl, Blue Clay acts as an aquiclude which collects percolating freshwaters from upper geological strata to form a ‘perched aquifer’, which, when saturated, seeps out from spring lines. The combination of surface and subsurface waters creates mesic habitats within sheltered areas, including gullies, rills, and boulder screens, which, in some years, maintain a ver-

dancy well into the dry season. Among the plant species that occur in such environments is the Fennel (*F. vulgare*), one of the larval host-plants of *P. machaon*, which also tends to colonize the verges of cultivated fields and valley banks, both common landscape features in Gozo. Steppic habitats, along with garrigue- steppe mosaics are also fairly common biotopes on the island of Gozo, where *R. chalepensis* can occur and where another potential larval host-plant (*Ferula melitensis* Brullo, C., Brullo, Cambria, Giusso, Salmeri & Bacch.) is frequent, along with numerous other floral species which can provide important resources for nectaring. In fact, according to the trajectories from telemetry data, the tagged butterflies appeared to prefer navigating between hills with extensive agricultural or steppic land cover, such as the lower elevations between the villages of Xagħra and Xewkija, and, likewise, between Għasri and Iż-Żebbuġ, rather than hill-topping (a common behavior for *P. machaon*) over the far more exposed hills, plateaux and buttes.

The tagged butterflies demonstrated similar trajectories with telemetry readings indicating that they eventually made their way towards the northern coast of the island of Gozo covering a minimum distance of >16 km in 17 days, then moved inland again. Notwithstanding the more extensive telemetric data available, the present study focuses on the initial days following release, in particular, the time when the released specimens crossed the channel from Comino to Gozo. From telemetric data collected during field monitoring sessions, it appeared that P.m.1 ♂ undertook the crossing during the latter part of the morning of June 30th, while P.m.2 ♂ crossed the Comino - Gozo strait by mid-afternoon of the same day. P.m.3 ♀ seemed to have crossed over to the larger island by mid-morning of July 1st, as the day progressed and after temperatures had risen sufficiently. P.m.3 ♀ appeared to have spent time on the Santa Marija and San Niklaw promontories before undertaking the crossing, potentially in search of nectaring opportunities within the gardens of the hotels in an otherwise karst-dominated coastal area.

Fig. 5 — Tracking the butterfly specimens on foot on the island of Comino, and by motorboat between the islands.

Following the tagging and release of the chameleon specimens at Buskett, on mainland Malta, the radio signal was monitored over the course of 17 field sessions between 5th and 21st August 2021 (Fig. 6). A total of three chameleon specimens were tagged, comprising one male and two females. The male chameleon (SPEC code: *C.c.1* ♂ - freq. 150.061 MHz), travelled the farthest of the three tagged individuals, covering a minimum distance of 92.9 m during nine days of successful tag deployment. However, subsequent to the readings of the 9th day, the radio signal from this tag was being transmitted from within a rubble wall close to its last recorded location. *C. chamaeleon* is not typically known for taking refuge in dry stone rubble walls and, given it was quite evident that the tag was not ‘moving’, it was surmised that a predator, such as *Hierophis carbonarius* (Bonaparte, 1833) (Green Whip Snake) or *Mustela nivalis* Linnaeus, 1758 (Least Weasel), both frequent species in the Buskett woodland habitat, took the chameleon as prey, leaving behind the tag with the remains of the carcass. It may be worth adding that during five of the nine field survey sessions, the male was located foraging on the ground. The females, on the other hand, were both found on dense, shrubby vegetation and remained so throughout the field monitoring period. One was found on a *Pistacia lentiscus* shrub (SPEC code: *C.c.2* ♀ - freq.

150.121 MHz), while the other on *Hedera helix* (Common Ivy) (SPEC code: *C.c.3* ♀ - freq. 151.121 MHz). Throughout the monitoring period, *C.c.2* remained within the confines of a particular thicket which consisted of *P. lentiscus* and *Laurus nobilis* (Bay Laurel) and covered a minimum distance of 59.4 m over 16 days. At times, due to the dense growth of the thicket, GPS accuracy was somewhat reduced, and it was not always possible to spot this tagged chameleon. Notwithstanding, on such infrequent occasions a strong telemetry reading reliably indicated the approximate location, which was then estimated by means of triangulation. During 11 of the 16 field sessions, this chameleon specimen (*C.c.2*) was spotted on or had readings originating from within a *P. lentiscus* at an average height of 2.5 m. *C.c.3* was not monitored for as long a period as *C.c.2*. Observations were carried out over a total of 6 days and, according to telemetry recordings, it is estimated to have covered a minimum distance of 52.7 m, a distance which appears to be discordant with that registered by *C.c.2* over a period of 16 days. Telemetry readings from *C.c.3* originated from a section of woodland which impeded access due to dense *H. helix* growing over a three-metre wall, with the portion above it being an afforestation site surrounded by dense stands of *Arundo donax* (Great Reed), and thickets of *P. lentiscus*. After six days of field monitoring, a telemetry reading from this chameleon indicated a complete lack of mobility, which, it was assumed, was due to the specimen having potentially fallen prey to a predator such as *H. carbonarius*, which has the ability of swallowing the individual chameleon whole, along with the radio tag, or a *Tyto alba* (Barn Owl), which would have flown away and carried the chameleon out of signal range. During the remainder of the field monitoring sessions, attempts were made to 'pick up' the signal from *C.c.3*, even from within other areas of the Buskett woodland and its outer periphery, however without success. Throughout the monitoring phase, observations were also made on the arboreal habits of *C. chamaeleon*, which additionally included randomly encountered individuals that did not form part of the tagging and monitoring process of the present study. The vast majority of specimens were observed on branches of *Populus alba* or within the dense shrubbery provided by mature large shrubs of *P. lentiscus*, generally, at an average height of two metres above the ground; one individual was also noted on *H. helix*. Worthy of note is the species' observed preference for dense vegetation that extended to the ground and which, in addition, had branches stretching out and merging into the foliage of adjacent trees. Such unbroken plant cover acts as a dependable conduit for movement within thickets, whilst simultaneously maintaining a physical linkage to the woodland floor.

Fig. 6 — The different trajectories followed by the three chameleon specimens (top to bottom: C.c.1, ♂ in blue; C.c.2 and C.c.3, ♀♀ in red).

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